

PERCEPTION OF VIRTUAL REALITY AS AN INSTRUCTION TOOL AMONG PRESERVICE TVET TEACHER EDUCATORS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN RIVERS STATE

*¹Legborsi Nwineh (PhD), ²Ekwueme Orikoha (PhD) and ³Kelechi Casmir Ezinma

^{1&2}Department of Vocational and Technology
Education Rivers State University, Port Harcourt

³Industrial Training Fund

*Correspondence author email: nwineh.legborsi@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

Understanding preservice TVET teacher educators' perception on the usefulness of virtual reality is key to integration and effective preparation of TVET teachers for utilization of the technology. The study investigated preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of virtual reality in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Four research questions guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted with a total of 52 study participants. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire with internal consistency coefficient of 0.89. Data gathered were analysed with mean. Result showed that the respondents had positive perception on the usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme. Similarly, the preservice TVET teacher educators had positive perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme. It was further found perceived some challenges that could limit effective usage of virtual reality for instructional delivery in technical education programme. Generally, it was concluded that although the preservice TVET teacher educators perceive virtual reality to be a useful instructional tool for technical education programme, there is need for consideration of the potential challenges. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that virtual reality should be adopted in the teaching and learning of practical content in technical education.

Keywords: Virtual reality, augmented reality, technical and vocational education, instructional delivery, perception of virtual reality, usefulness of virtual reality.

Introduction

The integration of digital technologies into education offers significant benefits for instructional delivery across all levels of the educational sector. In light of this, over time, institutions of learning have gradually embraced emerging technologies to enhance teaching and learning towards preparing students for the modern workplace. Integration of emerging technologies is particularly critical in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET), which emphasizes hands-on skills and practical competencies. Among the different of technologies gaining attention in this TVET, Virtual Reality (VR) stands out as an important tool for enhancing instructional delivery.

Virtual reality refers to a three-dimensional computer simulation of the environments which users can interact with using special electronic devices including headsets, gloves, or motion sensors (Radianti *et al.*, 2020).

Virtual reality (VR) applications in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) can be grouped into immersive and non-immersive virtual reality applications. The immersive or full immersive virtual reality applications are the most advanced form.

They utilize head-mounted displays (HMDs) and motion-tracking technology to transport users into completely virtual environments with 360-degree experiences (Freina & Ott, 2015). Some systems also integrate augmented reality (AR) and mixed reality (MR) to blend real-world and virtual elements, expanding the spectrum of possibilities for instructional innovation in TVET. They are widely used to replicate real-world technical tasks such as welding, automotive repair, and electrical work. They provide learners with opportunity to practice skills in a safe, risk-free environment and repeat procedures as needed for mastery (Abdul Hamid *et al.*, 2024; Leong, 2024). Non-immersive VR uses standard computer screens to simulate environments, allowing interaction through conventional devices like keyboards and mice. Examples are virtual laboratories, Scenario-based VR and educational VR games among others. Virtual laboratories provide opportunities for experimentation and skill development without the hazards or costs associated with physical labs. They are particularly, useful healthcare, engineering, and science (Leong, 2024; Smutny, 2022). Scenario-based VR training which enable learners to develop soft skills such as teamwork, communication, and customer service through interactive, lifelike situations (Leong, 2024). Educational VR games combine gamification with skill acquisition to boost engagement and learning outcomes (Oyelere *et al.*, 2020).

Virtual reality offers significant benefits in education as it can improve motivation, engagement, motivation, retention, and skill acquisition and learning outcomes, particularly when technical and pedagogical barriers are properly addressed and aligned with instructional goals (Lampropoulos & Kinshuk, 2024; Radianti *et al.*, 2020; Parong & Mayer, 2018). In Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET), virtual reality offers immersive, interactive environments that closely simulate real-world scenarios. VR allows learners to practice technical skills in a risk-free setting. It also provides opportunity for repeated practice and error correction without the hazards or costs associated with traditional hands-on training (Leong, 2024). Virtual reality provides learners opportunity to visualize complex procedures and operations and as a result of this, enhances learner engagement, motivation, and retention (Allcoat *et al.*, 2021; Leong, 2024; Makransky *et al.*, 2019). VR also makes learning more accessible to different categories of learners such as those with disability, those located in remote areas as well as those with limited resources (Leong, 2024; Rajamanickam *et al.*, 2024). Empirical evidence shows that VR has positive effect on psychomotor skills, knowledge acquisition, and spatial abilities, which are essential in TVET (JulianAbich *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, VR can be tailored to meet evolving industry demands (Leong, 2024; Rajamanickam *et al.*, 2024). Although issues such as cost particularly initial cost of deployment, infrastructure, and instructor training are notable, integrating VR into TVET presents opportunity for effective delivery (Leong, 2024; Rajamanickam *et al.*, 2024; JulianAbich *et al.*, 2021; Allcoat *et al.*, 2021).

A number of empirical studies have been conducted on preservice TVET teachers' and educators' perception on virtual reality (Antón-Sancho *et al.*, 2024; Baxter and Hainey, 2019; Criollo-C *et al.*, 2024; Domingo & Bradley, 2018; Cooper *et al.*, 2019; Farsi *et al.*, 2023; Hagge, 2020). However, studies which specifically focused on perception of preservice TVET teachers and or preservice TVET teacher educators in tertiary institutions in Nigeria were scarce in the literature. Cooper *et al.* (2019) investigated the pre-service teachers' perceptions about VR, Specifically, the study examined their beliefs about the capacity of VR as a teaching and learning tool. The result of the study showed that participants were interested in VR, they perceived that VR was very engaging and

would have positive effect on learning. They were also willing to use VR. Another study by Domingo and Bradley (2018) investigated the perception of master of arts preservice teachers on the use and value of virtual reality. The result showed that students had positive perception about the usefulness of virtual reality. Similar results were obtained by Antón-Sancho *et al.*, 2024, Criollo-C *et al.* (2024), Farsi *et al.* (2023), Hagge (2020), Baxter and Hainey (2019) and Lund and Wang (2019). There is need therefore to understand how TVET teacher educators perceive virtual reality.

Understanding how lecturers and students perceive VR as an instructional tool is essential for effective integration and sustainability of the technology in educational settings. Their perceptions can influence not only the adoption of VR tools but also their effective utilization and pedagogical alignment. If students perceive virtual reality to be engaging, useful, and aligned with their learning needs, they are more likely to embrace and benefit from it. Similarly, lecturers' perceptions affect how confidently and effectively they would be willing to and eventually incorporate VR into their instructional delivery (Bower *et al.*, 2020). In TVET, where experiential learning and technical competences are paramount, aligning perceptions with instructional outcomes can foster meaningful technology adoption and optimum student achievement. This study is significant because it addresses a growing gap in the literature regarding the perception and readiness of TVET educators to adopt VR as an instructional tool. By investigating TVET teacher educators' perceptions on virtual reality in tertiary institutions, the study offers evidence to guide institutional decision-making, capacity-building, and policy formulation for educational innovation in TVET.

Purpose of the Study and Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to investigate the perception of virtual reality as an instruction tool among preservice TVET Teacher educators and students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. To address this purpose, three research questions guided the study which are as follows.

1. What are the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the ease of use of virtual reality for instructional delivering in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. What are the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
3. What is the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
4. What are the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the challenges associated with the use of virtual reality for instructional purpose in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The sample for the study was 52 which comprised preservice TVET teacher educators from three tertiary institutions (Rivers State University, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku that offer technical education programme in Rivers State. Instrument for data collection was a validated survey questionnaire which was which had

internal consistency reliability coefficient of .89 obtained through Cronbach Alpha. The respondents were requested to indicate their perception of the usefulness of virtual reality as a tool for instructional delivery, usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme, usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme and their perception of the challenges associated with the use of virtual reality for instructional purpose in technical education programme. The responses were structured on a four-point rating scale ranging from Strongly Disagreed (SD) with a score of 1, Disagreed (D) with a score of 2, Agreed (A) with a score of 3 and Strongly Agreed (SA) with a score of 4. A total of 52 copies of the instrument was administered and a total of 52 was retrieved and used for data analysis. Data gathered were analysed using mean.

Result

Research Question 1: What are the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the ease of use of virtual reality for instructional delivering in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Responses for Ease of Use of Virtual Reality towards Knowledge Gain

S/N	ITEM STATEMENTS	Lecturers (n=52)		
		M	S.D.	RMK
1	I think it will be easy to operate virtual reality.	3.10	0.98	A
2	I think it will be easy for me to use gadgets associated with virtual reality.	3.00	0.97	A
3	I think it will be easy for me to learn to use virtual reality.	3.13	0.95	A
4	I think with the instruction in the user manual, I will be able to use virtual reality.	3.04	0.93	A
5	I think it will not be difficult to understand the operation of virtual reality.	3.08	0.90	A
6	Using virtual reality for instructional purpose will be easy.	2.98	1.04	A
7	The functions in virtual reality are easy to use.	3.13	0.82	A
	Grand Mean	3.07	0.94	A

Source (Field Data; A = Agree)

The result from Table 1 shows that the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result shows that they had positive perception of Ease of use of virtual reality towards knowledge gain. This is evident by mean responses being greater than 2.50 all the items. Furthermore, grand mean responses of 3.07 confirms that the preservice TVET teacher educators perceived that it will be easy to use for instructional delivery in technical education.

Research Question 2: What are the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Responses for Usefulness of Virtual Reality in Students' Motivation

S/N	ITEM STATEMENTS	Lecturers (n=52)		
		M	S.D.	RMK
1	Virtual reality can boost students' engagement on learning.	3.12	0.92	A

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2	Virtual reality could enhance students' participation in learning activity.	3.21	0.87	A
3	Virtual reality could enhance students' attention for learning.	3.00	1.01	A
4	Virtual reality could makes learning more interesting.	3.02	0.98	A
5	I think virtual reality would make learning to be enjoyable.	3.04	0.99	A
6	I think virtual reality would stimulate learning interest among learners.	3.31	0.90	A
7	Virtual reality would be effective in enhancing the attractiveness of instruction in technical education programmes.	3.08	1.03	A
	Grand Mean	3.11	0.96	A

Source (Field Data; A = Agree)

The result from Table 2 shows that the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result shows that they had positive perception of Ease of use of virtual reality towards knowledge gain. This is evident by mean responses being greater than 2.50 all the items. Furthermore, grand mean responses of 3.11 confirms that they perceived that virtual reality will be useful in motivating students for learning in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What is the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Responses for Usefulness of Virtual Reality towards Knowledge Gain

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	Lecturers (n=52)		
		\bar{x}	S.D.	RMK
1	Virtual reality could help to concretize abstract concepts.	3.56	0.50	A
2	Virtual reality could enhance easy understanding of complex topics.	3.48	0.50	A
3	Virtual reality could be a useful tool for teaching concepts not possible in classroom environment.	3.35	0.62	A
4	Virtual reality could be useful for exposing students to practical experience that may be dangerous to conduct in workshops or classroom.	3.40	0.63	A
5	Virtual reality could be a useful tool for enhancing creativity among students.	3.58	0.50	A
6	Virtual reality could be a useful tool for supporting learning by doing.	3.58	0.50	A
7	Virtual reality could enhance easy understanding of complex topics.	3.65	0.48	A
8	Virtual reality could serve as a useful tool for enhancing instructional delivery among teachers.	3.42	0.50	A
9	Virtual reality could be a useful tool for enhancing students' effectiveness in learning.	3.40	0.50	A
10	Virtual reality could serve as a useful tool for boosting academic achievement among students.	3.35	0.62	A
11	Virtual reality could serve as a tool for safely preparing students of technical education for field training.	3.48	0.50	A

12	Virtual reality is a cost effective way of delivering practical training in technical education.	3.25	0.59	A
13	I do not think virtual reality could be useful in teaching and learning of practical activities in technical education.	2.79	1.14	A
14	I do not think virtual reality could enhance learning.	2.48	1.18	D
Grand Mean		3.34	0.63	A

Source (Field Data; A = Agree)

The result from Table 3 shows that the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result shows that they had positive perception of Ease of use of virtual reality towards knowledge gain. This is evident by mean responses being greater than 2.50 all the items. Furthermore, grand mean responses of 3.34 confirms that they perceived that virtual reality will be usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question 4: What are the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the challenges associated with the use of virtual reality for instructional purpose in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Table 4: Mean Responses for Challenges to Using Virtual Reality for Instruction

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	Lecturers (n=52)		
		\bar{x}	S.D.	RMK
1	High cost of facilities needed for implementing virtual reality system could be a challenge to its utilisation in technical education.	3.42	0.50	A
2	Closeness of virtual reality application to modelled scenario could be a potential issue associated with its usage for instruction in technical education.	3.12	0.65	A
3	Concern for health implications of immersive virtual reality is a potential challenge to its usage for instruction in technical education.	3.02	0.58	A
4	Students' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality could be a potential issue to its implementation for instruction in technical education.	3.19	0.69	A
5	Teachers' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality could be a potential issue to its implementation for instruction in technical education.	3.27	0.60	A
6	Students' attitude towards virtual reality could be a potential issue to its implementation for instruction in technical education.	3.42	0.50	A
7	Teachers' attitude towards virtual reality could be a potential issue to its implementation for instruction in technical education.	3.58	0.50	A
8	Adequacy of instructional model underlining a virtual reality system could be a potential issue in its effective use for instruction in technical education.	3.58	0.50	A
Grand Mean		3.32	0.56	A

Source (Field Data; A = Agree)

Result from Table 4 shows that the lecturers perceive that the listed issues could be challenges to using virtual reality for instructional delivery in technical education. For example, they

generally agreed that teachers' and students' attitude towards virtual reality could be a potential issue in utilizing it for instructional delivery ($x=3.42$ for lecturers for item 6) and ($x=3.58$ for item 7). Furthermore, a grand mean response of 3.32 confirms that the respondents agreed that the listed issues could serve as challenges to using virtual reality for instructional delivery in the study area.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one sought to find out the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the ease of use of virtual reality for instructional delivering in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result shows that the respondents agreed that: it will be easy to operate virtual reality; it will be easy for me to use gadgets associated with virtual reality; it will be easy for me to learn to use virtual reality; with the instruction in the user manual, using virtual reality will be easy; it will not be difficult to understand the operation of virtual reality; using virtual reality for instructional purpose will be easy; the functions in virtual reality are easy to use. This result is similar to the result obtained by Cooper et al. (2019) who found that participants were interested in VR, they perceived that VR was very engaging and would have positive effect on learning. The result also corroborates the result by Domingo and Bradley (2018) who found that students had positive perception about the usefulness of virtual reality.

Research question two sought to find out the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result shows that the respondents agreed that: virtual reality can boost students' engagement on learning; Virtual reality could enhance students' participation in learning activity; virtual reality could enhance students' attention for learning; virtual reality could makes learning more interesting; virtual reality would make learning to be enjoyable; virtual reality would stimulate learning interest among learners; virtual reality would be effective in enhancing the attractiveness of instruction in technical education programmes. This result is similar to the result obtained by Lund and Wang (2019) who conducted a study to ascertain the impact of virtual reality on students' motivation to learn as well as its effect on students' academic performance in library and information studies in eastern Kansas, USA. Lund and Wang from their study found that students exposed to instruction through virtual reality had improvement in their level of motivation. Furthermore, the result agrees with that of Antón-Sancho et al. (2024) who found that respondents had positive perception of virtual reality.

Research question three sought to examine the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result showed that the respondents agreed that virtual reality could help to concretize abstract concepts, virtual reality could enhance easy understanding of complex topics, virtual reality could be a useful tool for teaching concepts not possible in classroom environment, virtual reality could be useful for exposing students to practical experience that may be dangerous to conduct in workshops or classroom, virtual reality could be a useful tool for enhancing creativity among students, virtual reality could be a useful tool for supporting learning by doing, virtual reality could enhance easy understanding of complex topics, virtual reality could serve as a useful tool for enhancing instructional delivery among teachers, virtual reality could be a useful tool for enhancing students' effectiveness in learning, virtual reality could serve as a useful tool for boosting academic achievement among students, virtual reality could serve as a tool for safely preparing students of technical education for field training, virtual reality is a cost effective

way of delivering practical training in technical education. They also agreed that virtual reality could be useful in teaching and learning of practical activities in technical education. Furthermore, the preservice TVET teacher educators disagreed to the statement that virtual reality cannot enhance learning in technical education. This is an indication that the respondents had positive perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. This result agrees with the results by Criollo-C et al. (2024), Farsi et al. (2023), Hagge (2020) and Baxter and Hainey (2019). Who similarly found positive perception on utilizing virtual reality for instruction.

Research question four sought to find out the preservice TVET teacher educators' perception of the challenges associated with the use of virtual reality for instructional purpose in technical education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The result shows that they agreed that high cost of facilities needed for implementing virtual reality system, closeness of virtual reality application to modelled scenario, concern for health implications of immersive virtual reality, students' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality, teachers' perception of the usefulness of virtual reality, students' attitude towards virtual reality, teachers' attitude towards virtual reality and adequacy of instructional model underlining a virtual reality system are potential challenges that could be associated with usefulness and effectiveness of virtual reality in instructional delivery in technical education. This result agrees with the result by Pfeil, Ang and Zaphiris (2009) who conducted a study to ascertain the issues and challenges faced in using virtual reality for educational purposes among students, teachers and institutions. Pfeil, Ang and Zaphiris found challenges associated with using virtual reality to involve technical challenges such as technicality that may be associated with using the tool. The result also agrees with the view of Abdelaziz, Alaa El Din and Senousy (2014) that challenges associated with using virtual reality for teaching and learning include: teaching activity used in the virtual environment (e.g. presentations, tutorials, discussion, field trips, among others).

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the preservice TVET teacher educators had positive perception about the usefulness of virtual reality in instructional delivering in technical education programme. It was also concluded that the preservice TVET teacher educators had positive perception on the usefulness of virtual reality in motivating students for learning in technical education programme. Similarly, the preservice TVET teacher educators had positive perception of the usefulness of virtual reality in helping students gain knowledge in technical education programme. Furthermore, it was concluded that the preservice TVET teacher educators perceived some challenges that could limit effective usage of virtual reality for instructional delivery in technical education programme. Generally, it was concluded that although the preservice TVET teacher educators perceive virtual reality to be a useful instructional tool for technical education programme, there is need for consideration of the potential challenges.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of this study, the following recommended were made:

1. Considering the usefulness and effectiveness of virtual reality in enabling users have a sense of reality, it should be adopted in the teaching and learning of practical content in technical education.
2. Funds should be provided by Government and supported by non-governmental

agencies to make virtual reality tools available for use in instructional delivery in technical education.

3. Feedbacks should be given to designers and producers of virtual reality on the potential challenges perceived to be associated with using virtual reality for instructional purpose.
4. Such feedback could help in redesigning for enhance usage, especially for instructional purpose in technical education.

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